

Use cases for benchmarking workflows identified

Report on Milestone 3.3 of ELIXIR-STEERS

Introduction

In the framework of **ELIXIR-STEERS**, **task 3.3** aims to extend the OpenEBench community-led evaluation feature. This extension will enable the technical benchmarking of workflows used for common analyses in the Life Sciences domain based on reference datasets.

For that purpose, from the ELIXIR-STEERS Task 3.3 perspective, a software has been developed to obtain a set of technical metrics. Such metrics should enable the assessment of efficiency and environmental impact of software executions. This software is the [Execution Metrics Collector](#), which gathers low-level technical metrics from Linux processes, which are then used to derive high-level indicators, including computational carbon footprint estimations. The [Technical Metrics live document](#) describes the low and high-level community-led metrics.

The identification of use cases for benchmarking workflows has been carried out in collaboration with ELIXIR-STEERS WP2, several ELIXIR Communities and other relevant Life Sciences communities, and is presented in [Milestone 3.3](#) report. From the use cases identified, we will obtain low- and high-level metrics that will enable assessing the workflow executions' carbon footprint impact. We will connect those workflows with popular managers systems like Galaxy to gather usage. Altogether will provide us with valuable information about reproducibility and the reuse of workflows by the different scientific communities in ELIXIR and, potentially, beyond.

OpenEBench local metrics collector

The [Execution Metrics Collector](#) has been created to gather efficiency and green technical metrics when executing software. Low-level metrics will be gathered, enabling the assessment of high-level metrics. This software consists of a python script and a set of bash scripts to monitor, collect, and visualise metrics of a given Linux process or a given command line. The [README](#) of the project describes most of the files generated by the collector and all the metrics gathered by it. The [Technical Metrics live document](#) describes the low and high-level community-led metrics.

This code makes it possible to measure **low-level technical metrics** of a complete tree of processes in several time series, which includes:

- Time series of spawned (sub)processes
- Time series of aggregated metrics of all the (sub)processes
- Time series of specific process technical metrics

From the collected low-level metrics, we can derive **high-level metrics** that estimate the computational carbon footprint. The high-level metrics have been obtained from [GreenAlgorithms4HPC](#). This code aims to obtain process execution statistics extracted from SLURM logs. Furthermore, the code is designed to be

extensible, allowing integration with additional data sources to enhance the accuracy and scope of carbon footprint estimations.

Methodology

From Task 3.3, we engaged with several ELIXIR Communities, through ELIXIR-STEERS WP2 and other relevant channels, to identify and request pilot workflows for testing the newly developed Executions Metrics Collector software. Additionally, we have also engaged with other communities from the Life Sciences domain, beyond ELIXIR-specific ones, which have provided us with workflows for testing the implementation.

The aim is to collect metrics from the provided workflows, which can be analysed using different approaches depending on the specific use cases. Possible approaches for technical benchmarking include analysing:

- Comparison of different workflows performing the same function: Standardized reference (synthetic) datasets can be used to ensure fair and consistent evaluation, allowing workflows of the same type to be tested under comparable conditions.
- Assessment of a single workflow with different datasets: This approach helps evaluate the robustness and adaptability of workflows across varying data inputs.
- Analysis of the same workflow across different versions: Comparing workflow versions provides insights into improvements, regressions, and performance variations over time.

Analyzing the collected metrics enables us to assess the impact and usage of software, ensuring workflow reproducibility and promoting reuse. Additionally, this analysis can help identify the most critical components of workflows, providing insights for optimisation and improvement, with reference to ELIXIR-STEERS milestone [M3.4](#).

Selected use-case workflows for Community-led evaluation in OpenEBench

All use cases related to Task 3.3 of STEERS are registered in the [Use-Cases tracking document](#), which is a live document containing all potential use cases identified and their status. For the current Milestone M3.3, we include only those use cases that have been tested with test datasets, ensuring their compatibility with the Execution Metrics Collector software. Other relevant workflows have been identified but have not yet been tested; they haven't been included as use cases in M3.3, but can be considered for the future development of the task.

Single Cell Community

Workflow name	nf-core/scrnaseq
Main contact/s	Dayana Yahalomi, Dan Ben-Avraham (WEIZMANN, IL)
Workflow purpose	nf-core/scrnaseq is a bioinformatics best-practice analysis pipeline for processing 10x Genomics single-cell RNA-seq data.
Workflow repository	Github: https://github.com/nf-core/scrnaseq/tree/4.0.0
Documentation	Github: https://github.com/nf-core/scrnaseq/tree/4.0.0
Datasets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Toy dataset of two paired end samples (tested), described at https://github.com/nf-core/test-datasets/raw/scrnaseq/samplesheet-2-o.csv <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ https://raw.githubusercontent.com/nf-core/test-datasets/scrnaseq/testdata/cellranger/Sample_X_S1_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz ■ https://raw.githubusercontent.com/nf-core/test-datasets/scrnaseq/testdata/cellranger/Sample_X_S1_L001_R2_001.fastq.gz ■ https://raw.githubusercontent.com/nf-core/test-datasets/scrnaseq/testdata/cellranger/Sample_Y_S1_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz ■ https://raw.githubusercontent.com/nf-core/test-datasets/scrnaseq/testdata/cellranger/Sample_Y_S1_L001_R2_001.fastq.gz ■ https://raw.githubusercontent.com/nf-core/test-datasets/scrnaseq/testdata/cellranger/Sample_Y_S1_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz ■ https://raw.githubusercontent.com/nf-core/test-datasets/scrnaseq/testdata/cellranger/Sample_Y_S1_L002_R2_001.fastq.gz ○ Example data from 10X website (https://www.10xgenomics.com/datasets/5k_Human_Donor2_PBMC_3p_gem-x). ○ Folder with the downloaded data, plus the reference genome and sample sheet. https://owncloud.incpm.weizmann.ac.il/index.php/s/mPFBNbWdu3tlprh <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ To download the dataset, registration is required.

Microbiome Community

Workflow name	MGnify Amplicon workflow
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Main contact/s	Paul Zierp (University Freiburg, DE), Bérénice Batut (IFB, FR)
Workflow purpose	This is the beta version of the v6.o MGnify amplicon analysis pipeline, which first and foremost, is a refactor of the existing v5.o amplicon analysis pipeline, replacing CWL with Nextflow as its workflow management system. This pipeline re-implements all existing closed-reference v5.o features, and makes multiple significant changes and additions.
Workflow repository	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ MGnify Amplicon workflow (Nextflow version) https://github.com/EBI-Metagenomics/amplicon-pipeline <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Test successful with commit o85a6c2bff73a2062eeeb98072e8693aa733ee65 ○ Galaxy Port of the MGnify Amplicon Pipeline (v5). Main workflow: https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/1274 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Galaxy language. Not tested yet.
Documentation	Blog post: Galaxy Project – MGnify v5
Datasets	<p>Toy dataset: two paired end samples (tested)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● https://raw.githubusercontent.com/nf-core/test-datasets/viralrecon/illumina/amplicon/sample1_R1.fastq.gz ● https://raw.githubusercontent.com/nf-core/test-datasets/viralrecon/illumina/amplicon/sample1_R2.fastq.gz ● https://raw.githubusercontent.com/nf-core/test-datasets/viralrecon/illumina/amplicon/sample2_R1.fastq.gz ● https://raw.githubusercontent.com/nf-core/test-datasets/viralrecon/illumina/amplicon/sample2_R2.fastq.gz

3DBioinfo Community

Workflow executor name	SCIPION
Main contact/s	Jose Maria Carazo, Lola Sánchez de Lara (CNB-CSIC, ES)
Workflow purpose	SCIPION is an image processing framework for obtaining 3D models of macromolecular complexes using Electron Microscopy (3DEM). It integrates several software packages and presents a unified interface for both biologists and developers. Scipion allows you to execute specialized workflows combining different

	software tools installed as plugins, while taking care of formats and conversions. Additionally, all steps are tracked and can be reproduced later on.
Workflow repository	SCIPION example template workflow at WorkflowHub: https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/599
Documentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scipion webpage: https://scipion.i2pc.es/ • SCIPION Github - installation: https://scipion-em.github.io/docs/release-3.0.0/docs/scipion-modes/how-to-install.html#:~:text=to%20contact%20us-,Installing%20other%20plugins,plugin%20can%20be%20easily%20installed • Template: https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/599
Datasets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Toy dataset: https://scipion.cnb.csic.es/downloads/scipion/data/tests/OSCEM_metadata/ • Template: https://scipion-em.github.io/docs/release-3.0.0/docs/facilities/facilities-workflows.html#creating-custom-dynamic-templates • Internal stress tests (to be tested)

IDP Community

Workflow name	CAID
Main contact/s	Damiano Piovesan, Mahta Mehdiabadi, Silvio Tosatto (UNIPD, IT)
Workflow purpose	Community-based blind test to determine the state-of-the-art in predicting intrinsically disordered regions and the subset of residues involved in binding. Participants submit software, not predictions. The software is standardized and made available through the CAID Prediction Portal web server
Workflow repository	https://caid.idpcentral.org/
Documentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CAID documentation: https://caid.idpcentral.org/portal/documentation • Del Conte et al. 2023, Proteins, https://doi.org/10.1002/prot.26582 • Necci et al. 2021, Nature Methods, https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-021-01117-3
Datasets	The CAID team will run the Execution Metrics Collector and subsequently provide a link to the datasets used.

Proteomics Community

Workflow name	WOMBAT-P pipelines
Main contact/s	Veit Schwämmle (SDU, DK), Salvador Capella-Gutierrez (BSC, ES)
Workflow purpose	<p>WOMBAT (WORKflow Metrics, Benchmarking and AnalyTics in Proteomics) community has their reference workflows for the analysis of label-free proteomics data (using files from the proteomics metadata standard SDRF), originating from LC-MS experiments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MaxQuant + NormalyzerDE • SearchGui + Proline + PolySTest • Compomics tools + FlashLFO + MSqRob • Tools from the Trans-Proteomic Pipeline + ROTS <p>This community hosts their reference workflows at https://github.com/wombat-p , which also hosts a meta-workflow which integrates all of them https://github.com/wombat-p/WOMBAT-Pipelines</p>
Workflow repositories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meta-workflow - https://github.com/wombat-p/WOMBAT-Pipelines • https://github.com/wombat-p/MaxQuant-Workflow • https://github.com/wombat-p/Proline-Workflow • https://github.com/wombat-p/Compomics-Workflow • https://github.com/wombat-p/Transproteomic-Pipeline
Documentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WOMBAT-P: Benchmarking Label-Free Proteomics Data Analysis Workflows https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jproteome.3c00636 • Github - https://github.com/wombat-p/WOMBAT-Pipelines
Datasets	<p>Output and configuration files provided by the community:</p> <p>https://github.com/wombat-p/WOMBAT-P_Processed</p>

Other workflows that are not associated with a specific ELIXIR Community

SAREK

Workflow name	SAREK
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Main contact/s	Paula Iborra (BSC)
Workflow purpose	nf-core/sarek is a workflow designed to detect variants on whole genome or targeted sequencing data. Initially designed for Human, and Mouse, it can work on any species with a reference genome. Sarek can also handle tumour / normal pairs and could include additional relapses.
Connection with a Community	Translational Bioinformatics Network (TransBioNet) in Spain, which INB/ELIXIR-ES coordinates. TransBioNet members were the experts group that was involved in IMPACT-Data project, which worked on the Sarek workflow.
Workflow repository	Github - https://github.com/nf-core/sarek/tree/3.5.1 ELIXIR - Tools and Data Services Registry - https://bio.tools/nf-core-sarek WorkflowHub - https://workflowhub.eu/workflows/1020 Dockstore - https://dockstore.org/workflows/github.com/nf-core/sarek
Documentation	Github - https://github.com/nf-core/sarek/tree/3.5.1
Datasets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Synthetic toy sample dataset , single end: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ https://github.com/nf-core/sarek/blob/5fe5cdf171e3baed603b3990cab7f7fd3fcb992/tests/csv/3.0/fastq_single.csv <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ https://raw.githubusercontent.com/nf-core/test-datasets/modules/data/genomics/homo_sapiens/illumina/fastq/test_1.fastq.gz ■ https://raw.githubusercontent.com/nf-core/test-datasets/modules/data/genomics/homo_sapiens/illumina/fastq/test_2.fastq.gz ○ Synthetic sample patient HCC1395, paired end: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ https://github.com/nf-core/test-datasets/blob/24cdbea48c4415a29f668a724ce602fef8fed813/testdata/csv/HCC1395_WXS_somatic_full_test.csv <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Normal sample HCC1395N: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> s3://ngi-igenomes/test-data/sarek/SRR7890919_WES_HCC1395BL-EA_normal_1.fastq.gz s3://ngi-igenomes/test-data/sarek/SRR7890919_WES_HCC1395BL-EA_normal_2.fastq.gz ■ tumour sample HCC1395T: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> s3://ngi-igenomes/test-data/sarek/SRR7890918_WES_HCC1395-EA_tumor_1.fastq.gz s3://ngi-igenomes/test-data/sarek/SRR7890918_WES_HCC1395-EA_tumor_2.fastq.gz

Next steps

- The plan is to keep interacting with interested community representatives and other stakeholders to extend the use cases-based workflows to have a more comprehensive and broad list of workflows to facilitate the metrics gathering process. Indeed, some workflows have been identified as potential candidates for technical benchmarking. However, they have not yet been tested. The next step is to test them with the Execution Metrics Collector using a toy dataset. If successful, they will be added to the [Use-Cases tracking document](#) and considered proper use cases for future technical benchmarking.
- Capture proposed metrics by executing identified workflows with the proposed datasets, either reference, synthetic or ad-hoc ones. The metrics collected during these executions will be analysed and shared with the corresponding Communities to identify gaps in the generated metrics. Additionally, the results will contribute to the software assessment of each specific workflow.
- Compare the proposed metrics with the ones available in usegalaxy.eu and propose mechanisms to extend, implement, or map their metrics with the ones proposed here in STEERS.

Conclusions

The identified use cases will be the basis for obtaining efficiency and green metrics through the Execution Metrics Collector. Analysing the technical metrics that will be obtained and estimating computational carbon footprints will successfully support the ELIXIR-STEERS Task 3.3 objective of benchmarking resource usage for computational tasks.

Ongoing collaboration with the selected ELIXIR Communities will support the continuous improvement of the proposed technical metrics, ultimately enhancing benchmarking standards and promoting sustainable software execution practices.

As a summary, the most relevant aspects exposed in this Milestone 3.3 include:

- **Successful implementation and initial validation** of the Execution Metrics Collector across various workflows provided by ELIXIR Communities, and using toy datasets. The selected workflows come from ELIXIR Communities such as **Single Cell, Microbiome, 3DBioinfo, IDP, and Proteomics**.
- **The identification of benchmarking strategies** allows workflow performance assessment under different conditions and datasets. The identified strategies are comparing different workflows performing the same function, assessing a single workflow with different datasets, and analyzing the same workflow across different versions.
- Additional workflow testing will be conducted with reference and more realistic datasets, prioritizing the integration with Galaxy workflows manager to gather workflows usage in real scenarios.

References

Publications

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